

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Employability study bachelor of science in entrepreneurship graduates of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology San Isidro Campus

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Abstract

The employability of graduates can be effectively measured by evaluating the efficacy of the programs given by various universities and institutes. The use of tracer studies, which are essential in offering insightful feedback on how relevant these initiatives are to the dynamic labor market. A particular study was designed to ascertain the employment status of graduates who completed the Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship program between 2017 and 2021 at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, specifically at the San Isidro Campus. To achieve this goal, a descriptive research method was employed, utilizing an adopted survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. This approach was chosen for its effectiveness in gathering detailed information about the graduates' current employment situations. The results of the study were quite revealing, indicating that out of 505 graduates 365 alumni who participated, that graduates from batch 2019-2020, were majority were female, were 25-26 years of age, CSE professional eligible, were mostly not National Certificate holder, majority were employed, as accounting clerk, with monthly salary range of 10,000-19,999, assigned in accounting and finance department, having a position of marketing assistant. On the data on their first job, the results graduates find their job less than 1 year after graduation, stayed on their first job for less than 1 year, were on contractual basis and the reason for leaving their first job is for better salary. The factor that influence them to find their present job is from recommendation from relatives and friends. The reason for delay in employment is caused by delay in issuance of school credentials. And for competitive skills of the graduates communication skill is very important to be more competitive. These findings are significant as they offer insights into the employment trends and the market absorption rate of graduates from this specific program, thus providing a measure of the program's success in preparing students for the job market.

Keywords: Tracer Study; Program Effectiveness; Labor Market Relevance; Employment Status; Business Entrepreneurship Graduates; Descriptive Research Method.

1. Introduction

One important component of higher education, which aims to prepare students for a successful transition into the workforce, is the employability of graduates. Employability is more than just having a degree; it's about having a variety of abilities, know-how, and qualities that appeal to employers. Employers are looking for graduates with a strong work ethic, practical skills, and adaptability in addition to academic qualifications in today's competitive and changing employment market.

Today's challenging economic situation means that it is no longer sufficient for a new graduate to have knowledge of an academic subject; but it is necessary for a student to gain the skills which will enhance their prospects of employment (Ramirez, et al., 2014). Higher Education Institution as considered as the center of civilization must be responsive and involve in developing individuals through its programs offerings has obligation to keep track of their graduates and to

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determine accountability and whether or not their programs have impacted on their clientele (Hazaymeh, et al., n.d.). One fundamental problem of education and training is that they must be geared to the current and future needs of societies undergoing social and economic change. Education and training must be planned in flexible dynamic process and not in static specifications. It should be always capable of changes. Specific consideration of the country have to be taken into account such that effective and efficient education and training even the resources are scarce.

Higher education institutions take great satisfaction in offering a program that fosters students' overall development. Students are shaped by their experiences with academic success, personal growth, and social responsibility. All educational institutions strive to produce capable corporate executives who will soon be the driving forces behind social stability, economic growth, and nation-building (De La Salle University, n.d.). Furthermore, Higher Educational Institution (HEI) is challenge in balancing the development of higher education and professional relevance of academic teaching (Matejamelink and Samopavlin, 2009). Learning success parameter is measured through the employability of graduates, type of employment and the length of landing on their first job (Taberdo, A. et. al, 2021). Government agencies have been encouraging educational institutions and employers to work together to address employability issues (Lowden, Hall, Elliot and Lewin, 2011). It is considered as the pride and honour of every academic institution to produce globally competent employed graduates.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) envisions to develop globally competent and empowered human resources, who are ready to the challenges and demands of the 21st century through the Higher Education Institution (HEIs), (Torres, et al., 2017). According to Mercado as mentioned by (Ramirez, et al., 2014), states that the Commission on Higher Education in the Philippines initiates to conduct Graduate Tracer Study among selected Higher Education Institution in order to gather data that would show if HEI's offering courses or programs that produce graduates meet the needs of industry and society. HEI's should be able to align their efforts with the manpower needs of industry (CHED CMO #38,2.2006, 11, s.1999).

Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology San Isidro Campus is one of the Higher Education Institution (HEIs) which is responsible in providing curriculum that serves as the foundation of the graduates to develop their skills and knowledge in order to be prepared in the work environment. One of the program being offered by Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology-San Isidro Campus Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship under the College of Management and Business Technology. It is designated to produce graduates that possess a formulary of business operations and equip them with critical decision making skills for strategic and executive work necessary for competing in the ever changing world of business. The program empowers students with a basic and clear understanding of the function of every decision in a company, be it on marketing, finance, operations, human resources and office management. Trainings in this program emphasize to become an entrepreneur thus, prepare them into managerial and supervisory position.

Employability is defined as a graduate's capacity to land a fulfilling job; hence, obtaining a job should not take precedence over being ready for work in order to prevent the creation of a fictitious employability index for each individual. The College of Management and Business Technology at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology-San Isidro Campus (NEUST-SIC) is one with the goal of providing competitive training to business management students in order to give them the best chance to be employed. To monitor the performance of the college and the relevance of its curriculum, this graduate tracer study was conducted.

In an integrated narrative that merges various scholarly perspectives, the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology San Isidro Campus, through its College of Management and Business Technology, initiates a tracer study focusing on the career trajectories and achievements of its Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship graduates. This initiative, inspired by Cuadra, L. et al. (2019), is essential for appraising and refining academic programs, allowing the university to collect vital information about its graduates' career progressions, educational foundations, and the relevance of their studies to the demands of their careers. Building on this, Santos (2023) underscores the importance of tailored Human Resource Management practices in enhancing organizational effectiveness, highlighting the need for educational programs to be in sync with current business requirements. Santos (2020) also delves into the crucial role of faculty commitment, illustrating their profound understanding of their organizational roles and their significant contributions towards achieving institutional objectives. This commitment, together with factors like market conditions, competitive trends, and social responsibilities, is pivotal in crafting an educational experience that is both relevant and impactful. The collective insights from Cuadra et al. (2019), Hazaymeh and Dela Pena (2011), and Santos (2020) emphasize the importance of the tracer study, not just in assessing the university's past educational achievements but also in ensuring that its curriculum aligns with the dynamic requirements of the job market and modern organizational practices.

Conducting a research study on employability of graduates provides information on whereabouts of graduate which might broaden the perspectives among administrators, faculty and students. Relevant information such as income, economic sector, current job title, working time, duration of search for the first job, methods of job search, values develop and practice in work and skills acquire are essentially for an institution. According to (Schomburg, 2003) as mention by (Hazaymeh, et al., n.d.), a tracer study is a empirical study which provides valuable information for assessing the results of the education and training of specific program of an institution. Through a tracer study the Higher Institution can able to information that identify the gap between the program being offered and skills required by job market which will serve as basis for revision of the curriculum and improvements. The acquisition of knowledge in the undergraduate specialization, skills and competencies will also promote productivity, efficiency and expertise in graduates' present job (Valdez, 2017). On employment status, the provision of written agreement notwithstanding and regardless of the oral agreement of the parties, an employment shall be deemed to be regular where the employee has been engaged to perform activities which are usually necessary or desirable in the usual business or trade of the employee; except where the employment has been fixed for specific project or undertaking the completion or termination of which has been determined at the same time of engagement of employee or where the work or service to be performed is seasonal in nature and employment is for the duration of the season. A study by (Orejana, et al., 2010) showed that BSBA graduates indicates that 91% were employed, with 20% supervisory positions and 4% holding managerial positions. Content or topics covered by the programs is found to be the main strength in the aspect of curriculum as supported by 45% of the respondents while lack of applications and exposures came out to have more exposures and applications as expressed by 45% of the respondents. On the number of employed and unemployed, (Diestro, 2013), most of the graduates are employed on the course they finished while who did not land job mentioned the following reason: busy as housewives and some pursue to higher studies (masteral and doctorate).

The study embarked on an insightful journey to uncover the employment trajectories of the graduates from the College of Management and Business Technology at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, San Isidro Campus, focusing on those who completed their studies between 2017 and 2021. The core objective was to paint a detailed picture of these graduates, beginning with their profiles. This included the year they graduated, their gender, any eligibility they might have, and whether they held any national certifications. Moving beyond mere demographics, the study delved into the nature of their employment. It aimed to categorize the types of jobs these alumni had secured, including the specifics of their roles such as job titles, monthly salaries, the departments they were assigned to, their positions within these departments, and, importantly, the locations of their jobs, categorized by region and province. The narrative of their early career paths was also a point of focus. The study sought to chronicle the time taken by these graduates to find their first job post-graduation, the duration they stayed in these initial roles, their first job titles, and the reasons why they eventually left these positions. Understanding the journey doesn't stop at the first job, the study also aimed to explore the factors that influenced the graduates in securing their present jobs. This exploration extended to uncovering the reasons behind any delays in employment they might have experienced after graduation. Lastly, a key aspect of this study was to evaluate the competitive skills possessed by these graduates, skills that presumably contributed to their employability and success in the job market. Each of these elements combined to offer a comprehensive view of the employment status and career progression of the graduates from the College of Management and Business Technology at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology.

2. Material and methods

The study employed descriptive research methodology, utilizing a survey as the primary tool for data collection. As highlighted by McCombes in 2023, descriptive research is particularly suited for investigations aimed at identifying characteristics, frequency, trends, and categorizations within a subject area. This approach aligns well with the study's goal of delineating various aspects of graduate employment.

To effectively address the research questions, the researchers developed a structured questionnaire. This instrument was used by Alvarez, M.T. et. al (2022) in their study entitle " A graduate's employability study of Bachelor of Science in entrepreneurship of Isabela State University, Philippines". However, it was not merely adopted as is; the questionnaire underwent significant modification and refinement by the researcher to better suit the specific objectives of this study. On the first part was purely modified it adds the profile of the respondents such year graduated, sex, eligibility and national certification. On the second part which describe the data of the employment aside form variables type of employment status, type of employment, job title of the graduates and monthly salary there were two(2) additional variable were added assigned department and position. These modifications were not done haphazardly; they were the result of thoughtful suggestions for improvements. The last part of the instrument variable were purely adopted. To ensure the reliability and effectiveness of the questionnaire, a preliminary 'dry run' was conducted. This trial involved a selected group of graduates, whose feedback was instrumental in finalizing the questionnaire.

The study's respondents comprised a substantial group of 365 graduates from the years 2017 to 2021. The distribution of the survey was conducted personal distribution by students from the College of Management and Business Technology, ensuring a hands-on and targeted approach. In addition to personal distribution, the researchers also utilized digital platforms, reaching out to other potential respondents through emails and Facebook accounts. This multi-channel approach was critical in ensuring a comprehensive reach across the graduate population.

Once the data was collected, it underwent a rigorous process of analysis and interpretation. The researchers employed frequency and percentage distribution methods to analyze the data. This approach allowed for a clear and concise presentation of the findings, facilitating an understanding of the various dimensions of graduate employment and trends over the specified period. The study's methodology, therefore, was comprehensive, combining both traditional and digital means of data collection and employing robust analytical techniques to derive meaningful insights.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 showed the profile of the respondents. As seen on the table, 294 or 58.22% of the total respondents were employed; 71 or 14.06% were not employed, 140 or 27.72 % were cannot be traced. It can be seen from the table that graduates from 2019–2020 have the highest employability with 44 or 74.58% and year 2018-2019 has the lowest rate of 89 or 52.35 %. For not employed batch 2018-2019 has the highest number or unemployed which is 35 or 20.59% and for the lowest 2020-2021 which has 0. For not traced batch 2016-2017 has the highest number which is 67 or 38.28% and lowest is batch 2020-2021 which is zero.

Table 1 Year Graduated

Year Graduated	Total Graduates	Employed	%	Not Employed	%	Cannot Be Traced	%
2020-2021	4	4	100	0	0	0	0
2019-2020	59	44	74.58	9	15.25	6	10.17
2018-2019	170	89	52.35	35	20.59	46	27.05
2017-2018	97	62	63.92	14	14.43	21	21.65
2016-2017	175	95	54.28	13	7.43	67	38.28
Total	505	294	58.22	71	14.06	140	27.72

As gleaned on the table, majority of the BS Entrepreneurship graduates were employable. It signifies that graduates possess the necessary skills and knowledge needed by job market which manifest that the programs offered by the College of Management and Business Technology are align with the policies, standard and guidelines. BS Entre graduates from 2019-2020 are expected to have higher percentage of employability since they are few to trace and fresh graduates.

“Not Employed” until this time because of their personal reasons like “taking care of their parents or children” and some admittedly “they just don’t fine their luck to be employed”. Graduates shows Filipino values of close family ties. Familism, a cultural value that emphasizes warm, close, supportive family relationship and that family is prioritized over self (Campos, et al., 2014). Sacrificing for their love ones were become their choice in life because of the current situation they are facing.

“Cannot be traced” are graduates which cannot be located on facebook or email and other social media account. Graduate destination surveys pose the difficulty of tracing graduates years later when their contact details may have changed (Toit, 2014). Graduates opted to use alias or not their real name on their social media account.

Table 2 shows the frequency of respondents according to sex. It can be seen that majority of the respondents were employed are female which 229 or 62.74%) and 136 or 37.26% were male.

Table 2 Gender of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	136	37.26
Female	229	62.74
Total	365	100

As seen on the table, majority of the BS Entrepreneurship graduates were female. It demonstrates that more women are considering enrolling in courses related to entrepreneurship. According to Bullough, A. et. al. (2021), women appear to be more susceptible to the development of entrepreneurial behavior. In other words, exposure to parental role models has a significantly positive impact on women's attitudes toward entrepreneurship compared to those of males. He went on to say that exposure to entrepreneurship education has a larger impact on women's perceived control over their entrepreneurial behavior than it does on men, and that exposure to parental role models has a considerably more positive impact on women's attitudes toward entrepreneurship than it does on men. Finally, the registrar's data revealed that a majority of the students enrolled were female.

Table 3 shows the age of respondents. It can be seen from the table that 156 or 42.72% graduates aged from 25 and 26 years old, followed by 93 or 25.48% are those ages from 27 and 28 years old, followed by aged 23-24 year old which is 91 or 24.93 %, followed by aged 29 year old and above which is 14 or 3.84 % and lastly 21-23 years which is 11 or 3.01%.

Table 3 Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
21-22 years old	11	3.01
23-24 years old	91	24.93
25-26 years old	156	42.74
27-28 years old	93	25.48
29 years old and above	14	3.84
Total	365	100

As indicated on the table majority of the graduates 25 and 26 years old. According to Zhao, Hao et. al. (2021), when it comes to entrepreneurial graduates, age is an intriguing element. Some believe that because of their creative thinking and willingness to take chances, younger people have a better chance of success. Others claim that elder entrepreneurs have a wealth of experience and expertise to draw from, which gives them an advantage. Finally, it appears that age is only one of several characteristics that can influence an individual's success as an entrepreneur. Graduates, regardless of age, must focus on expanding their skills and expertise, finding mentoring and assistance, and constantly learning and adapting to the ever-changing corporate scene.

Table 4 Eligibility

Eligibility	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
CSE Sub Professional	47	12.88
CSE Professional	158	43.29
National Certificate	10	2.74
Not Applicable	150	41.09
Total	365	100

Table 4 showed the eligibility of the respondents . As seen on the table, majority of the respondents took CSE Professional which is 158or 43.29%, followed by “ Not Applicable” which is 150 or 41.09%, “CSE Sub Professional” got 47 or 12.88% and, “ National Certificate” got the lowest percentage which 10 or 2.74%.

As discussed on the table, most of the respondents took CSC Professional examination for them to have more chance to enter in government service. According to Dandeevee (2023), the civil service exam serves to guarantee that people with the necessary skills and expertise are appointed to public sector positions by requiring candidates to pass a standardized test. This makes it more likely that qualified applicants will fill open positions in the public sector.

Table 5 shows the type of national certificate of the respondents. It can be gleaned on the table, “ Not Applicable” got the highest percent which is 355 or 97.26 % of the respondents. while “Communication Technology” which is , “Events Management”, “Lifelong Learning Skills” NCIII Cookery”, “NC II Agriculture” got the lowest percentage which is 1 or .27%.

Table 5 Type of National Certificate

National certificate	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Communication Technology	1	.27
Events Management Services NCIII	1	.27
Lifelong learning skills	1	.27
NAPOLCOM PNP Entrance Exam	2	.54
NC III Cookery	1	.27
NC II Agriculture	1	.27
NCII COMPUTER HARDWARE SERVICING	3	.82
Not Applicable	355	97.26
Total	365	100%

Majority of the graduates were not NC holder. These proves that BS Entre graduates are fully equipped of knowledge and skill s needed to be employable. TESDA National Certification is now being assessed in Higher Education Institutions for its effectiveness to enhance individual’s competencies and skills for their future job in the industry Manalo. J. P. A (2018).

3.1. Employment of BS Entrepreneurship Graduates

Table 6 shows the employment status of the respondents. The table revealed that 246 or 67.40% of BS Entrepreneurship graduates are currently employed, 31 or 8.94% are OFW, 17 or 4.66% are self-employed, and 71 or 19.45 % are unemployed.

Table 6 Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Employed	246	67.40
OFW	31	8.49
Self-employed	17	4.66
Unemployed	71	19.45
Total	365	100

It can be depicted on the table, majority of the BS Entrepreneurship graduates were employable. It signifies that graduates possess the necessary skills and knowledge needed by job market which manifest that the programs offered

by the College of Management and Business Technology are align with the policies, standard and guidelines. As discussed in Table 1 BS Entre graduates from 2019-2020 got the highest employability rate .

“OFW” graduates based on unstructured interview are mostly employed at Middle East country like Saudi Arabia, UAE, and Dubai.

“Self-employed” are those graduates who have courage to start their own business. Mostly of the graduates were engage in franchising business like milk tea shop, online selling, agricultural supplies, restaurant business, furniture shop and upholstery business.

“Not Employed” until this time because of their personal reasons like “taking care of their parents or children” and some admittedly “they just don’t fine their luck to be employed”. Graduates shows Filipino values of close family ties. Familism, a cultural value that emphasizes warm, close, supportive family relationship and that family is prioritized overself (Campos, et al., 2014). Sacrificing for their love ones were become their choice in life because of the current situation they are facing.

Table 7 shows the job title status of the respondents. As a result, the majority of graduates worked in “Office Staff” which is 88 or 24.11%, followed by “Sales specialist” with 77or 21.10%, followed by business owners with 64 or 17.53%, followed by “accounting” which is 54 or 14.79%“, followed by “ cashier” which is 37 or 10.14%; “ Human Resource and Call Center agent has same percentage which is 3 or .82%; “Bookkeeping, production, production operators and Housewife” has the same percentage which is 2 or .54%; and lastly “ admins staff, Area Sales Leader, Assistant Surveyor, Assistant Team Leader, Auditor, Branch Secretary, Coordinator, Crew, Herd and young stock technician, Leader/Head, Logistic and Warehouse Assistant, Pharmacy Assistant, Police officer, and Professional Teacher” has same response of 1 or .27%.

Table 7 Job Title of Graduates

Job Title of Graduates	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Admin staff	1	0.27
Area Sales Leader	1	0.27
Assistant surveyor	1	0.27
Assistant team leader	1	0.27
Auditor	1	0.27
Bookkeeping	2	0.54
Branch Secretary	1	0.27
Business Owner	64	17.53
Call Center Agent	3	0.82
Cashier	37	10.14
Coordinator	1	0.27
Crew	1	0.27
Herd and youngstock technician	1	0.27
House wife	2	0.54
Human Resource	3	0.82
Leader/Head	1	0.27
Logistics and Warehouse Assistant	1	0.27
Manager	17	4.66
Office Staff	88	24.11

Operator	2	0.54
Pharmacy assistant	1	0.27
Police Officer	1	0.27
Production operator	2	0.54
Professional Teacher	1	0.27
Accounting	54	14.79
Sales specialist	77	21.09
Total	365	

As table discussed majority of the graduates employed in rank and file or clerical position. Since, they are newly employed it is given that they occupy in lower positions in the firm they belong to.

Table 8 show the salary per month of the respondents. As gleaned on the table, 181 or 49.59% has a salary of 10,000-19,999 which got the highest percentage while salary range of less than 10,000 which is 2 or .54% got the lowest percentage.

Table 8 Salary per Month

Salary per Month	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
10,000 – 19,999	181	49.59
20,000 – 29,999	84	23.01
30,000 – 39,999	5	1.37
40,000 and above	22	6.02
Less than 10,000	2	.54
N/A	71	19.54
	365	100

As seen in the table 7, graduates are typically non-management, non-supervisory employees in the Philippines general depends on the firm, position and qualifications of the employee. However, the salary of the employee in rank and file is commonly around 10,000 to 15,000 per month it is also depends on the firm and situation (Murillo, R.O., 2023).

Table 9 show the respondents assigned department. As seen in the table, “Accounting and finance” got the highest percentage which is 82 or 22.47%, followed by “sales” which is 78 or 21.37%; followed by “Marketing” which has 66 or 18.08%; followed by “HR” which is 45 or 12.33%; followed by “Operation Management” which is 37 or 10.14%; followed by “ Not Applicable” which has 20 or 5.47%; followed by “Treasury” which has 10 or 2.74% and lastly “ Information Technology” which got the lowest percentage which is 9 or 2.47%.

As can be seen on the table, majority of the graduates are employed in different department as business function. For small companies their function is divided to operations, marketing, human resources and finance while in some organizational structure are more complex and consists not only of these four departments but is further broken down into several theses includes distribution and logistics, sales and marketing, research and development, customer service, information technology, finance and accounting, corporate strategy, Human resource, communication, procurement, and quality management (Nasudrin, 2023). These means that graduates are competitive they are flexible they can able to do the task not only in one field of business but as well the other.

Table 9 Assigned Department

Assigned Department	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Accounting and Finance	82	22.47
HR	45	12.33
Information Technology	9	2.47
Marketing	66	18.08
Operations Management	37	10.14
Production Research and Development	18	4.93
Sales	78	21.37
Treasury	10	2.74
Not Applicable	20	5.47
	365	100

Table 10 shows position occupied by the graduates. As seen on the table, “ marketing assistant” got the highest percentage which is 38 or 10.41 % while “ Accounting staff”, “Area Sales Leader”, “Asssitant surveyor”, “Bracnh secretary”, “Chef”, “Compliance officer”, “Computer Programmer”, “Director of Marketing”, “Inspector”, “insurance Specialist”, “ Internal Sales”, “Pharmacy Assistant”, “police Officer”, “Professional Teacher”, Quality Assurance “ has same percentage and got the lowest percentage of 1 or .27%.

Table 10 Position of Respondents

Position	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Account Manager	2	0.54%
Accountants and Analysts	12	3.27%
Accounting Managers	17	4.63%
Accounting staff	1	0.27%
Area Sales leader	1	0.27%
Assistant cash manager	2	0.54%
Assistant surveyor	1	0.27%
Assistant treasurer	4	1.09%
Auditors	3	0.82%
Bank Teller	2	0.54%
Bookkeeping	7	1.91%
Branch Secretary	1	0.27%
Business owner	8	2.18%
Cash manager	14	3.81%
Cashier	27	7.36%
Chef	1	0.27%
Clerk	28	7.63%
Compliance officer	1	0.27%

Computer Programmer	1	0.27%
Computer Scientist	1	0.27%
Content marketer	2	0.54%
Credit and Collection Officer	2	0.54%
Customer Service Representative	5	1.36%
Digital strategist	2	0.54%
Director of marketing	1	0.27%
Director of treasury	2	0.54%
Financial Manager	2	0.54%
HR Assistant	17	4.63%
HR Director	2	0.54%
HR Executive	3	0.82%
HR Generalist	2	0.54%
HR Manager	16	4.36%
HR Specialist	2	0.54%
Industrial Production Manager	1	0.27%
Inspector	1	0.27%
Insurance Specialist	1	0.27%
Internal Sales	2	0.54%
IT Coordinator	1	0.27%
IT Security Specialist	1	0.27%
IT Technician	1	0.27%
Market analyst	3	0.82%
Marketing assistant	38	10.41%
Marketing coordinator	7	1.91%
Marketing executive	4	1.09%
Marketing manager	7	1.91%
Not Applicable	21	11.17%
Operations Manager	9	2.45%
Operations Research Manager	1	0.27%
Operator	7	1.91%
Pharmacy Assistant	1	0.27%
Police Officer	1	0.27%
Production manager	2	0.54%
Professional Teacher	1	0.27%
Quality Assurance Tester	1	0.27%
Research and Development Manager	4	1.09%
Research Manager	1	0.27%

Restaurant Manager	1	0.27%
Sales Agent	4	1.09%
Sales Executive	8	2.18%
Sales Manager	22	5.99%
Sales Representative	2	0.54%
Search engine optimization (SEO) specialists	2	0.54%
Senior Living Facility Server	1	0.27%
Store Crew	1	0.27%
Supervisor	1	0.27%
Support Specialist	2	0.54%
Systems Analyst	1	0.27%
Tax director	1	0.27%
Team Leader	1	0.27%
Tele sales	2	0.54%
Transaction services analyst	2	0.54%
Treasurer	6	1.63%
Workshop managers or team leader or plant manager	2	0.54%
	365	100.00%

As seen on the table, majority of the respondents are employable. The skills and ability learned during their school days were usable in the nature of their work. As a results graduates were employed in business related position. As seen in Table 9 most of the respondents were assigned in Marketing Department, thus it is right that most of the graduates have position as Marketing Assistant. The skills and conceptual knowledge that employers requires for marketing position different levels ranging from entry-or lower level jobs to middle and senior level position (Schelee, 2010)

3.2. Data on the First Job

Table 11 shows duration of looking for the job after graduation. As seen on the table, “Less than 1 year” got the highest percentage which is 216 or 59.18% and “more than 3 years” got the lowest percentage which is 6 or 1.64% .

Table 11 Duration of Looking for a Job After Graduation

Duration of Looking for a Job after Graduation	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
1 year to 2 years	135	36.99
2 years to 3 years	8	2.19
Less than 1 year	216	59.18
More than 3 years	6	1.64
	365	100

After college, it might be challenging to find employment. The University of Washington (UW) reports that "it takes the average college graduate three to six months to secure employment after graduation." (Meza,W. et al. 2020).

Table 12 table shows how long did the respondents stay in their first job. It can be seen that majority of the respondent stayed on their first job for “Less than 1 year” which is 166 or 45.48% while “more than 3 years” got the lowest percentage which is 5 or 1.37%.

Table 12 How long did they stay in their first Job

How Long did you Stay in your First Job	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1 year to 2 years	84	23.01
2 years to 3 years	20	5.48
Less than 1 year	166	45.48
more than 3 years	5	1.37
N/A	71	19.45
Still on the first Job	19	5.21
	365	100

Majority of the graduates are employable within 1 year hence they did not able to regularized in their first job since they stayed in their job for less than 1 year. Labor contractualization has long been a contentious issue in the Philippine socio politico-economic discourse. The issue, is more commonly associated with Endo or “end of contract,” is the unconscionable termination of employment of non-regular employees intended to circumvent the legal requirements afforded to regular employees.(Paqueo and Orbeta 2016, 2).

Table 13 shows the reason for leaving of the respondents. It can be seen on the table that, “Better Compensation” is the most reason why graduates leave their jobs with 73 or 20% of the total respondents while “Family circumstances” is the least reason while the graduates leave their job with 2 or .55%.

Table 13 Reason for Leaving

Reason for Leaving	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Better compensation	73	20
Better or different leadership	13	3.56
Career advancement	53	14.52
Career change to new industry	52	14.25
Company downturn	27	7.40
Company restructuring	38	10.41
Different work environment	19	5.21
Family circumstances	2	.55
Not Applicable	71	19.45
Professional development	17	4.65
	365	100

As seen in the table majority of the respondent are looking for greener pasture. One of the necessities of life can be fulfilled by means of income, namely wages or salaries. To get wages or salaries we are required to work professionally with the consequences of getting a bigger income(Darmawan, K. 2021). Career growth is a major factor in employee turnover. Employees desire to grow, learn, and develop. They desire the ability to envision a future with a company(Bahar, A.k.M. et.al. 2022.).

Table 14 shows the factors influenced them to find their present job. As gleaned on the table, “Recommendation from relatives and friends” got the most responses with 131 or 35.88%, followed by “ educational qualifications” with 68 or 18.63% of the respondents while “ Assistance of the placement office” got the least responses with 2 or .55%.

Table 14 Factors Influenced them to find their Present Job

Factors Influenced Them to Find Their Present Job	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Assistance of the Placement office	2	.55
Educational Qualification	68	18.63
Government employee office	7	1.92
Job fair/ DOLE	27	7.40
Media advertisement	38	10.41
On-line application	51	13.97
Personnel office thru advertisement of the company	7	1.92
Recommendation from former teacher	12	3.29
Recommendation from politicians	22	6.03
Recommendation from relatives and friends	131	35.88
	365	100

Most of the graduates depend their luck on recommendation from friend and relatives. Reflective of family influence over career orientation, some of the work values correlated with parents' educational and professional backgrounds (Llenares, et. Al, 2021). Assistance of the placement office got the lowest response since the University often conducted Job placement and base on unstructured interview graduates were not able to attend the job fair.

The table 15 shows the reason for delay in employment. Data implies that 99 or 27.91% of the respondents got delayed in their employment because of delay in issuance of school credentials, while "rest for 6 months after graduation got the least response with 1 or .27%.

Table 15 Reason for Delay in Employment

Reason For Delay in Employment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Available Jobs are not in the line with the Field of Specification	39	10.68
Delay in Issuance of Needed Documents	54	14.79
Delay in Issuance of School Credentials	99	27.12
Delay in taking/passing the CSE examination (as requirements)	9	2.47
Due to Pandemic	2	.55
Early marriage and/or pregnancy	12	3.29
Lack of financial support for the job hunting	14	3.84
No Immediate Vacancy	7	1.92
Not Emotionally Ready	13	3.56
Proximity of the work place	17	4.66
Rest for 6months before finding a job	1	.27
Stiff Competition for the Job	27	7.40
Not Applicable	71	19.45
	365	100

Most of the graduates are decisive in finding job hence the cause of delay because of the issuance of credentials. Base on unstructured interview the reason why there is delay in the preparation of student's credential because of limited staff .Hence there are student who find to have relaxation before looking for a job.

Table 16 shows the competitive skills of BS Entrepreneurship graduates. As can be seen from the table, item 9, "Communication Skills," received the highest weighted mean of 3.58 percent. Item 4&8, "Entrepreneurial Skills and Research and Extension Skills," received weighted mean of 3.51 percent. Item 2&6, "Human Relation/Interpersonal Skills and Problem Skills," received weighted mean of 3.49 percent. Item 7, "Core Value Formulation" received 3.48 percent. Item 1&5, "Critical Skills and Information Technology Skills," received 3.45 percent. Lastly, item 3, "Personality development" received the lowest weighted mean of 3.43 percent. Generally, the BS Entrepreneurship graduates evaluated the items on competitive skills as very important.

Table 16 Perceived Importance of Competitive Skills of Graduates

Item Statement	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
1. Critical Skills	3.45	Very Important
2. Human Relation / Interpersonal Skills	3.49	Very Important
3. Personality development	3.43	Very Important
4. Entrepreneurial Skills	3.51	Very Important
5. Information Technology Skills	3.45	Very Important
6. Problem Skills	3.49	Very Important
7. Core Value Formulation	3.48	Very Important
8. Research and Extension Skills	3.51	Very Important
9. Communication Skills	3.58	Very Important

Many firms consider competitive skills to be one of the most important requirements for hiring employees. BS Entrepreneurship graduates are included to this matter to fulfill the work market requirements. In general, it can be gleaned from the findings that most Graduates attribute primary value to abilities that demonstrate their ability to use business skills, connect with others through communication skills, or make effective relationships. According to Herry (2022), there are several abilities that can be applied in a variety of businesses. Entrepreneurial abilities, in particular, can comprise a wide range of skill sets such as technical skills, leadership and business management skills, and creative thinking. Because entrepreneurial talents can be used to a wide range of professional roles and industries, developing your entrepreneurial abilities may entail developing a variety of skill sets.

4. Conclusion

Based on the thorough analysis conducted, the researcher arrived at a conclusive understanding regarding the employability of graduates from the Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship program. It was observed that a significant majority of these graduates found employment. Mostly were female, with 25-26 years of age, with CSE professional with no TESDA certification. These positions were characteristically regular or permanent, and primarily with office staff as position, with salary or 10,000-19,999 range of salary, assigned in Marketing Department as marketing assistant . Graduates look for their first job for less than 1 year, and stayed in the company for less than 1 year with better compensation as main reason for leaving. The main factor that influence to their present job is through recommendation of relatives and friends. Delay in the issuance of school credentials as the main reason for delayed in employment. And Lastly Communication skills is considered as the most important competitive skills.

A key conclusion drawn from the study was the alignment of the employability skills acquired at the university with the job requirements sought by employers. The majority of respondents reported that the critical skills, Human Relation/Interpersonal skill, personality development, entrepreneurial skills, information technology skills, problem solving skills, Core value formation, research and extension skills and communication skills they gained during their academic tenure were "very important" in their chosen occupations. Furthermore, these skills were also deemed to be "highly developed," indicating a strong correlation between the university's educational offerings and the practical

demands of the job market. Among the various competencies, “communication skills” stood out as the most recommended by the graduates, suggesting that effective communication is a pivotal skill in the modern business environment.

This study underscored the marketability of BS Entrepreneurship graduates, evidencing their possession of the necessary skills and knowledge to not only secure employment but also to thrive in the competitive job market. To bolster this employability, the researcher suggested several interventions. Firstly, it was recommended that the university should invest in acquiring advanced materials and laboratory tools to enhance the learning and teaching experiences in both the Entrepreneurship and Marketing Management programs.

Moreover, the institution was advised to strengthen its linkages and partnerships to support a robust job recruitment program for its graduates. Periodic reviews of the curriculum were also suggested to ensure that it remains relevant and in tune with the evolving demands of the job market. Such revisions could make graduates more employable and prepared to meet industry needs.

The university was encouraged to consider integrating competency certification programs into the curriculum. This initiative could significantly increase the graduates' skill set, making them more attractive to potential employers not just locally, but on a global scale. By implementing these recommendations, the university could play a pivotal role in preparing its students for successful careers in Business Administration.

This tracer study will provide information about the employment status of graduates from the Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship, at the Campus over the past five years. This information may assist both the University and its instructors in identifying areas for growth and development, particularly in providing relevant preparation and training to Entrepreneurship students. Additionally, this study will serve as baseline data for other researchers conducting research on Business Administration programs.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

The researcher discloses any potential conflicts of interest, including affiliations with institutions, products, or any competing interests related to this manuscript or the outcome of its study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in this study.

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